

172 (22.5), 144 (12.5), 60 (36.0) and 55 (100.0, base peak). All these facts indicate the compound to be tetratriacontanoic acid, $\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{32}\text{CO}_2\text{H}$ (lit³, m.p. 98.2°). This appears to be the first report of its isolation from a plant source.

The benzene-chloroform (4 : 1) eluate gave a solid which was homogeneous on tlc. The solid on repeated crystallisation from benzene-chloroform mixture furnished needle shaped crystals (0.05 g), m.p. 132°. It was characterised as a mixture of stigmasterol (66.7%) and sitosterol (33.3%) in the usual manner by its positive Liebermann-Burchard test and comparison of spectral (ir, ¹H nmr and mass) data⁴ and finally co-glc⁵ of its acetate (m.p. 122°) with acetates of the authentic samples.

The alcoholic extract (10.0 g) on column chromatography through Si-gel afforded a homogeneous residue from ethyl acetate-methanol (9 : 1) eluate. The residue on repeated crystallisation from methanolic chloroform solution gave white crystals (0.035 g), m.p. 278–80°. It responded to positive Liebermann-Burchard test and showed ir and ¹H nmr spectra diagnostic⁶ of Δ^5 -sterolglycosides. The FD-ms⁷ of the compound revealed some significant peaks at 599 [$M+\text{Na}$]⁺ (10.9 percent), 577 [$M+\text{H}$]⁺ (20.0), 415 [Aglyc+H]⁺ (41.8), 397 [M -hexose+H]⁺ (100.0), 382 (60.0) and 256 (56.4), suggesting it to be a sitosterol-hexoside. The compound on hydrolysis with 2 N HCl in aqueous-methanol (1 : 1) gave sitosterol and D-glucose. Therefore, the glycoside was characterised as sitosterol- β -D-glucoside; the nature of glycosidic linkage was considered as β -from the coupling constant (6.5 Hz) of anomeric sugar proton at δ 4.72.

The presence of stigmasterol and sitosterol-glucoside was reported earlier⁸ from its sister species, *S. acmella*.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank I.I.C.B., Calcutta for ¹H nmr spectra, R.S.I.C., Lucknow for ir and mass spectra, R.S.I.C., Bose Institute, Calcutta for glc analysis, and U.G.C., New Delhi for financial assistance.

References

1. D. B. DEB, "The Flora of Tripura State", Today & Tomorrow, New Delhi, 1983, Vol. 2, p. 226.
2. B. DINDA and S. GUHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, 64, 376.
3. F. FRANCIS, A. M. KING and J. A. V. WILLIS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 999.
4. V. K. GARG and W. R. NES, *Phytochemistry*, 1984, 23, 2925.
5. G. W. PATTERSON, *Anal. Chem.*, 1971, 43, 1165.
6. W. SUCROW, *Chem. Ber.*, 1966, 99, 2765.
7. B. DOMON and K. HOSTETTMANN, *Phytochemistry*, 1985, 24, 575.
8. N. R. KRISHNASWAMY, S. PRASANNA, T. R. SESHADRI and T. N. C. VEDANTHAM, *Phytochemistry*, 1975, 14, 1666.

A New Withanolide Datumetelin from the Leaves of *Datura metel* L.

TARIQ MAHMOOD*, S. SALMAN AHMAD
and
AINE FAZAL

H. E. J. Research Institute of Chemistry, University of Karachi, Karachi-32, Pakistan

Manuscript received 11 January 1988, revised 14 March 1988, accepted 21 March 1988

A new withanolide datumetelin has been isolated from the fresh leaves of *Datura metel*¹ together with the previously known withanolide daturin². The structure of the new compound was established by spectroscopic data.

The leaves extract of *Datura* species are reported to contain mainly tropane alkaloids³ and some steroidal lactones⁴. Earlier we reported the isolation and characterisation of a tropane alkaloid⁵ and two withanolides^{2,6} from the leaves of *Datura metel*. Some withanolides have also been reported recently^{7,8} from the same plant. In this communication we report the isolation and structure elucidation of one more hitherto unknown withanolide, datumetelin (1) from the fresh undried leaves of *D. metel*.

Compound 1 was obtained as a white crystalline solid which formed rectangular plates on recrystallisation from ethyl acetate-methanol (9 : 1), m.p. 180–82°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} - 56^\circ$ (*c* 0.12 CHCl_3) having molecular formula $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{40}\text{O}_8$ (high resolution mass M^+ 468.2881); λ_{max} 210 nm (α, β -unsaturated ketone); ν_{max} 1685 (α, β -unsaturated carbonyl) and 1712 cm^{-1} (γ -lactone) characteristic of withanolides⁹. Apart from the molecular ion, mass spectra showed intense peaks at 437.2698 ($\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{37}\text{O}_4$) and 436.2618 ($\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{35}\text{O}_4$) resulting from the loss of methoxy group and methanol, respectively. A peak at *m/e* 365.2480 ($\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{35}\text{O}_2$) appeared by the loss of C-25 to C-27 along with their oxygen functions. The cleavage of D/E ring (C-17/20) gave peaks at *m/e* 269.1832 ($\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{25}\text{O}$) and 268.1822 ($\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{23}\text{O}$), with or without transfer of hydrogen. The ¹H nmr spectra exhibited two doublets of double doublets at δ 5.85 (1H, $J_{2,3}$ 10.1, $J_{2,4a}$ 2.9, $J_{2,4b}$ 1.1 Hz), 6.78 (1H, $J_{3,2}$ 10.1, $J_{3,4a}$ 4.9, $J_{3,4b}$ 2.5 Hz) and a doublet of triplet at δ 5.55 (1H, J 6.0 Hz) due to the olefinic protons H-2, H-3 and H-6, respectively. Three sharp singlets related to the methyl groups appeared at δ 0.67 (H-18), 1.22 (H-19) and 1.31 (H-28). The signals of H-27a and H-27b appeared as double doublets at δ 3.75 ($J_{27a,27b}$ 9.8, $J_{27a,28}$ 2.8 Hz) and 3.98 ($J_{27b,27a}$ 9.8, $J_{27b,28}$ 7.5 Hz). Whereas the H-25 resonated as double doublet ($J_{25,27a}$ 2.8, $J_{25,27b}$ 7.5 Hz) at δ 2.48.

The data recorded above is similar to that of daturilin, except the signal of H-25 which was absent in daturilin and the upfield chemical shifts and multiplicities of H-27a and H-27b due to the saturation of double bond between C-25 and C-27. These observations which are comparable with other withanolides¹⁰⁻¹², collectively led to the assignment of structure 1 for datumetelin.

Experimental

Melting point was recorded in glass capillary tube and is uncorrected. The uv and ir spectra were recorded on Shimadzu UV-240 and JASCO A-302 spectrophotometers, respectively. The ¹H nmr spectrum was recorded on a Bruker AM-300 spectrometer and mass spectra on Varian MAT-112 and MAT-312 double focussing spectrometers.

The fresh undried leaves of *D. metel* were soaked in ethanol, ground and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated (evaporation under reduced pressure at 45°). The resulting gummy mass was divided into 10% acetic acid and ethyl acetate soluble fractions. The ethyl acetate solution was concentrated under reduced pressure. The viscous sticky material was defatted with petroleum ether and the remaining residue was subjected to column chromatography (silica gel, 70-230 mesh, E. Merck). The petroleum ether (7 : 3) eluate was further subjected to thin layer chromatography (silica gel 0.2 mm, chloroform) affording datumetelin as a white crystalline solid, which on recrystallisation from ethyl acetate-methanol (9 : 1)

formed rectangular plates, m.p. 180-82°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 56^\circ$ (c 0.12, CHCl₃); λ_{max} (MeOH) 210 nm; ν_{max} (CHCl₃) 1712 and 1685 cm⁻¹; m/e (rel. int. %) 468.2881 (*M*⁺, calcd. for C₂₉H₄₀O₅, 468.2875, 90), 453.2636 (C₂₈H₃₇O₅, 4), 437.2698 (C₂₈H₃₇O₄, 14), 436.2618 (C₂₈H₃₅O₄, 60), 365.2480 (C₂₈H₃₅O₃, 40), 354.2210 (C₂₈H₃₃O₅, 5), 269.1832 (C₁₉H₂₅O, 12), 268.1822 (C₁₉H₂₄O, 16), 253.1598 (C₁₈H₂₁O, 18), 225.1270 (C₁₆H₁₇O, 24), 185.0972 (C₁₅H₁₅O, 30) and 171.0820 (C₁₅H₁₁O, 48); δ (CDCl₃) 0.67 (3H, s, H-18), 1.22 (3H, s, H-19), 1.31 (3H, s, H-28), 1.69 (1H, m, H-20), 1.85 (1H, dd, $J_{23a,23b}$ 13.1, $J_{23a,22}$ 4.3 Hz, H-23a), 2.02 (1H, dd, $J_{23b,22}$ 13.1, $J_{23b,23a}$ 2.0 Hz, H-23b), 2.48 (1H, dd, $J_{25,27a}$ 2.8, $J_{25,27b}$ 7.5 Hz, H-25), 2.81 (1H, dd, $J_{4a,4b}$ 21.3, $J_{4a,3}$ 4.9 Hz, H-4a), 3.30 (1H, dd, $J_{4b,4a}$ 21.3, $J_{4b,3}$ 2.5 Hz, H-4b), 3.40 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.49 (1H, dd, $J_{21a,21b}$ 13.5, $J_{21a,20}$ 3.0 Hz, H-21a), 3.75 (1H, dd, $J_{27a,27b}$ 9.8, $J_{27a,22}$ 2.8 Hz, H-27a), 3.90 (1H, d, $J_{21a,21b}$ 13.5 Hz, H-21b), 3.98 (1H, dd, $J_{27b,22}$ 7.5, $J_{27b,27a}$ 9.8 Hz, H-27b), 4.62 (1H, br s, $W_{1/2}$ 3.2 Hz, H-22), 5.55 (1H, dt, J 6.0 Hz, H-6), 5.85 (1H, ddd, $J_{2,3}$ 10.1, $J_{2,4a}$ 2.9, $J_{2,4b}$ 1.1 Hz, H-2) and 6.78 (1H, ddd, $J_{3,2}$ 10.1, $J_{3,4a}$ 4.9, $J_{3,4b}$ 2.5 Hz, H-3).

References

- S. SIDDIQUI, N. SULTANA, S. S. AHMAD and S. I. HAIDER, *Phytochemistry*, 1987, 26, 2641.
- Collected from Karachi, Pakistan in February 1987 and identified by Dr. S. I. ALI, Department of Botany, University of Karachi.
- R. L. CLARKE in "The Alkaloids", ed. R. H. MASNKE, 1977, Vol. XVI, p. 83, references cited therein.
- W. C. EVANS, R. J. GROUT and M. L. K. MENSAH, *Phytochemistry*, 1984, 23, 1717, references cited therein.
- S. SIDDIQUI, N. SULTANA, S. S. AHMAD and S. I. HAIDER, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1986, 49, 511.
- S. S. AHMAD, T. MAHMOOD and S. SIDDIQUI, *Heterocycles*, 1988, 27, 101.
- Y. OSHIMA, A. BAGCHI, H. HIKINO, S. C. SINHA, M. SAHAI and A. B. RAY, *Tetrahedron Lett*, 1987, 28, 2025.
- K. SHINGU, T. KAJIMOTO, Y. FURUSAWA and T. NOHARA, *Chem. Pharm. Bull*, 1987, 35, 4359.
- W. HERZ, K. AOTA and A. L. HALL, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1970, 35, 4117.
- I. KIRSTON, E. GLOTTER, D. LAVIE and A. ABRAHAM, *J. Chem. Soc. (C)*, 1971, 2032.
- E. GLOTTER, I. KIRSTON, A. ABRAHAM and D. LAVIE, *Tetrahedron*, 1973, 29, 1351.
- M. SAHAI and I. KIRSTON, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1984, 47, 527.